

INTERACTIVE LEARNING TASKS IN SCIENCE FOR GRADE 6 IN CALOY-AHAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL AN ACTION RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT:

This action research aimed to improve the performance level of the Grade 6 pupils in Science with the end goal of developing Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6 in Caloy-ahan Elementary School, Calubian North District, Division of Leyte during the school year 2016-2017. The descriptive survey method was used to elicit data that were needed to answer specific questions posed in this inquiry. The data gathered were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, and weighted mean. Based on the gathered data, the following were the findings of the inquiry: 1. The performance level of the Grade 6 pupils, which was interpreted as "Low Performing," where the mean percentage score obtained by the pupils was only 16%. 2. The majority of the performance standards in Science needed to be developed among Grade 6 pupils. 3. There were three (3) instructional materials utilized, Seldom Utilized by the teacher in teaching Science for Grade 6, and these were the Learning Kit, Modular Lesson-Type and Laboratory Learning Exercise with a 2.00 mean value. While the instructional materials, such as Interactive Learning Tasks, got a 1.00 mean value interpreted as Never Utilized, and the Existing Activities. Based on Lesson got 4.00 mean value was interpreted as Very Often Utilized and 4. The problems that got the highest mean value of 5.00 were Absence or lack of instructional materials, and Inadequate Science facilities and equipment. Indeed, this clearly conveys that the development of Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6 is vital. The practitioner decided to develop the Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6 that would be used during the teaching-learning process. Furthermore, the Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6 must be utilized properly to improve the performance level of the Grade 6 pupils in Science, develop the needed performance standards among pupils, and address the problem of teacher on lack of instructional materials.

KEYWORDS:

INTERACTIVE LEARNING, ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE, INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS.

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

3rd March 2026

5th March 2026

I. INTRODUCTION

Improving the academic performance of our students at both the elementary and secondary levels across the country, particularly in public schools, is one of the greatest concerns of everyone in the Department of Education. Concerted efforts are required to produce effective schools. According to Jacer (1993), effective schools are those that produce high-performing graduates. Toreno (2004) believes that superior education is possible with superior teachers. According to her, "A good teacher should not only have the know-what but also the know-how and know-why. In short, this implies that to improve the education of our youth, good and competent

teachers are indispensable.

The teachers have direct influence on students' academic development. May questions be asked: What factors could have contributed to poor academic performance? Could it be due to the lack of competence of teachers in the content of instruction or the lack of skills in constructing high-order thinking skills (HOTS) evaluation questions? Could it also be a lack of knowledge and use of teaching strategies and methods to make learning comprehensive and enjoyable? And could it be due to non-use of appropriate instructional materials, poor classroom management, and or lack of commitment on both the

pillars of education and the learner.

The purpose of Science Education is to develop skills among learners and to have a functional knowledge in the performance of their daily life activities. Scientific application is not only for a neither intellectual exercise for a few nor limited to Scientists and other Science enthusiasts. It has become an essential part of a man's working tool that provides the best way to cope effectively with everyday problems.

The Grade 6 teacher in Science of Caloy-ahan Elementary School, Calubian North District typically perceives the job as directly related to the amount of scientific content to which they can expose their children. He does not realize that the amount or the degree of knowledge in Science content will not help the children for more learning. Mastery of the science process skills is vital since the skills will be the tool in gaining more knowledge. The effect of wrong perception on the acquisition of scientific knowledge would lead the teacher to practice of letting the pupils copy scientific concepts actual experiencing and clear understanding. This is the most common method used by teacher.

Memorization of facts in Science will also lead to the development of wrong attitude towards the subject. Pupils will never enjoy in copying and memorizing scientific knowledge, hence, this action of improving the way of teaching Science, thus, improving the achievement of the pupils.

Several strategies were tried like fieldtrip, making of album, group reporting, and group research.

The use of fieldtrip in teaching did not give good results because many of the parents do not allow their children to go with the group due to financial constraints. Such approach would lead pupils to be absent and feel inferior with the others.

The construction of the album was critical. It made pupils destroy some books and references. Pupils cut pictures and some pages to be used in their albums.

The research group's reporting was crucial. Only the advanced pupils could do the assigned task. Slow learners were just considered as onlookers and helpers.

Teaching the basic performance standards is one of the expectations for Science literacy. Learning is more enhanced in an atmosphere of self- discovery through the use of the various science processes. Teachers often perceive that their intellectual authority is dependent on their knowledge of the truth. The issue on content is raised from the viewpoints of the preposition is offered that competent teachers may have thought, but instead need skills in the different performance standards.

The National Science Education Standard suggests that the teachers of Science must have a strong broad of scientific knowledge and approaches in teaching for them to understand the nature of scientific inquiry. In school, training was conducted, and teachers were made to attend. The training was focused on the mastery of the different

performance standards. The training conducted at the school level was not sufficient and effective since the achievement in Science for Grade 6 remained low. The use of the prepared modules was encouraged by some school heads, so the practitioner tried some ready-made modules. After several months of using the ready-made modules, the achievement of the pupils was low. With much experience, the teacher-investigator tried to improve the existing modules by adding enhanced learning activities. Despite all the cited interventions, pupils' achievement in Science did not improve.

The continuous results of having poor achievement in Science for Grade 6 made the practitioner decide to make Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6.

Pupils learn best by active, hands-on exploration and discovery. They make sense of the world by experiencing it physically. "Rachel Carson may have said it best," says Nancy Roser, Ed. D., Professor of Education at the University of Texas at Austin (Roser, Ed. D. 2017, Retrieved from: (2011) <http://education.utexas.edu/siteMap.php?error=404>). "Carson described children as learning from a 'sense of wonder.' This sense of wonder allows kindergarteners to become absorbed in the puzzles that surround them. They attempt to figure out those puzzles by exploring, constructing explanations, and asking more questions."

It is therefore important, necessary, and essential that modules developing the performance standards be properly used by the Grade 6 pupils. Hence, this study maximizes the child's potential through a variety of carefully selected and meaningful experiences, considering his interests and contributing individuals, able to make decisions that will prepare him for the more complex demands of future life.

II. OBJECTIVES

This action research aimed to improve the performance level of the Grade 6 pupils in Science with the end in view of developing Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6 in Caloy-ahan Elementary School, Calubian North District. Division of Leyte during the school year 2016-2017.

Specifically, this action research tried to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance level of the Grade 6 pupils in Science of Caloy-ahan Elementary School?
2. To what extent are the following performance standards in Science developed among Grade 6 pupils?
 - 2.1 The learners should be able to prepare beneficial and useful mixtures such as drinks, food, and herbal medicines
 - 2.2 The learners should be able to separate desired materials from common and local products
 - 2.3 The learners should be able to make a chart showing healthful habits that promote proper

functioning of the musculo-skeletal, integumentary, digestive, circulatory, excretory, respiratory, and nervous systems

2.4 The learners should be able to make an inventory of vertebrates and invertebrates that are commonly seen the community

2.5 The learners should be able to practice ways of caring and protecting animals

2.6 The learners should be able to make a multimedia presentation on how parts of the reproductive system of spore-bearing and cone-bearing plants ensure their survival

2.7 The learners should be able to make a flyer on how plants can be propagated vegetatively

2.8 The learners should be able to form discussion groups to tackle issues involving protection and conservation of ecosystems that serve as nurseries, breeding places, and habitats for economically important plants and animals

2.9 The learners should be able to produce an advertisement demonstrates road safety

2.10 The learners should be able to create a marketing strategy for a new product on electrical or light efficiency

2.11 The learners should be able to design an emergency and preparedness plan and kit

3. To what extent are the following instructional materials utilized by the teacher in teaching Science for Grade 6?

3.1 Interactive Learning Tasks

3.2. Existing Activities Based on Lessons

3.3 Learning Kit

3.4 Modular Lesson-type

3.5 Laboratory Learning Exercises

4. What are the problems met by the teacher in teaching Science among Grade 6 pupils?

5. What Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6 may be prepared based on the findings of this action research?

This inquiry tried to achieve the following objectives:

1. Motivate the teacher practitioner to use the Interactive Learning Tasks in Science to carry out delivery of daily instructional activities towards a more enjoyable and meaningful learning experience in Grade 6.

2. Improve the performance level in Science of the Grade 6 pupils in Caloy-ahan Elementary School, Calubian North District.

3. Arouse the curiosity and interest of children.

4. Develop performance standards for the Science of Grade 6 pupils.

5. Prepare Grade 6 pupils for formal academic work with a sense of being independent learners.

III. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the action research design to analyze and interpret data. It includes the research design, locale of the study, respondents, the instrument used, validation of instruments, data collection procedure, and statistical tools used in the study.

ACTION RESEARCH DESIGN

This inquiry aimed to improve the performance level of the Grade 6 pupils in Science with the end in view of preparing Interactive Learning Tasks in Science in Caloy-ahan Elementary School during the school year 2016-2017.

The achievement test was based on the performance standards listed in the K to 12 Curriculum Guide for Grade 6. The test was composed of 100 items. Pupils were asked to write the letter of the correct answer. This particular test was used to determine the performance level of the Grade 6 pupils in Science.

A teacher-made questionnaire was prepared that elicited data on the extent to which the performance standards were developed among Grade 6 pupils, extent to which instructional materials were utilized by the teacher in teaching Science such as Interactive Learning Tasks, Existing Activities Based on Lessons, Learning Kit, Modular Lesson-type, and Laboratory Learning Exercises, and the problems met by the teacher in developing Science performance standards among Grade 6 pupils.

After the administration of the test, the test score of each pupil was recorded and tallied. After which, the average scaled score of the class was computed.

The data gathered were analyzed using frequency counts, percentage and weighted mean. The analysis of data eventually provided the researcher the bases in preparing the Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6.

LOCALE OF THE INQUIRY

Caloy-ahan Elementary School is located in Barangay Kawayan, Bugtong, Calubian, Leyte, approximately 12 kilometers away, going southwest of Villalon Central School. There are 7 regular permanent teachers assigned to the school. The school has a land area of 550 square meters. Caloy-ahan Elementary School has a population of 183 pupils. Barangay Kawayan Bugtong is an upland, hilly, and agricultural community. The barrio folks are peace and loving people. Most of them are farmers and small-scale businessmen who sell their products to Naval, Biliran. Habal- habal or a single motorcycle is the only means of transportation during sunny days. Carabaos and horses replace the habal-habal during rainy days. The pupils go to school by walking. There is no cellphone signal in Caloy-ahan Elementary School, but there is electricity. Caloy-ahan Elementary School is an ideal school site free from cockpits, gambling dens, movie houses, and etc. It has an environment conducive to learning.

THE RESPONDENTS

The respondents of this action research were the twenty-five (25) Grade 6 pupils and the teacher in Caloy-ahan Elementary School, Calubian North District, Division of Leyte. Table I shows the total number of pupils in Grade 6.

As shown in Table 1, it could be gleaned that there were nine (9) male and sixteen (16) female pupils who were enrolled in Grade 6 as one class at Caloy-ahan Elementary School, Calubian North District. The total pupil-respondents was twenty-five (25) pupils.

TABLE 1

THE RESPONDENTS OF THE ACTION RESEARCH IN CALOY-AHAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL CALUBIAN NORTH DISTRICT

SCHOOL YEAR: 2016-2017

Sex	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Male	9	36%
Female	16	64%
TOTAL	25	100%

THE INSTRUMENTS

The instruments employed in the study were the teacher-made achievement test for the Grade 6 pupils and the survey questionnaire for the teacher.

Achievement Test for the Pupils: The achievement test for Science was prepared by the researcher designed to determine the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science. The content of the test was based from the K to 12 Curriculum. It was composed of 100 items.

The Survey Questionnaire for the Teacher: This instrument was composed of three parts. Part one of this research instrument was used to determine the extent to which the performance standards in Science were developed among Grade 6. The second part determined the extent to which the instructional materials were

utilized by the teacher in developing the Science performance standards, such as Interactive Learning Tasks, Existing Activities Based on the Lessons, Learning Kit, Modular Lesson-type, and Laboratory Learning Exercises. And the third part determined the problems met by the teacher in teaching Science among Grade 6 pupils.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Before the conduct of the survey, permission was sought from the Schools Division Superintendent through a formal letter. When permission was approved, the practitioner personally administered the survey questionnaire and achievement test to the teacher and to Grade 6 pupils, respectively. An orientation and explanation of the purpose of the study were discussed to the children so that true data could be gathered.

Each pupil was given the test paper to answer. They answered the questions by writing the letter of the correct answer on their paper. They answered in sixty (60) minutes.

On the other hand, the teacher answered the survey questionnaire by checking the number that best described the performance standards in Science developed among the Grade 6 pupil, the degree to which the instructional materials were utilized, and the problems met by the teacher in teaching Science among Grade 6 pupils. The teacher answered in five (5) minutes only.

STATISTICAL TREATMENT OF DATA

All data that gathered was tallied, organized, analyzed, and interpreted with the use of appropriate statistical tools.

The standard criteria set by the Department of Education in terms of performance level of pupils (DepEd No. 73, s. 2012), are as follows:

Mean Value	Qualitative Description
86%-100%	High Performing
66%-85%	Average Performing
65% and below	Low Performing

To determine the extent to which the performance standards in Science were developed among Grade 6 pupils, the following mean values and quantitative descriptions were used.

Mean Value	Qualitative Description
4.20-5.00	Outstandingly Developed
3.40-4.19	Very Satisfactorily Developed
2.60-3.39	Satisfactorily Developed
1.80-2.59	Unsatisfactorily Developed
1.00-1.79	Need to be Developed

To determine the extent to which the instructional material utilized by the teacher in teaching Science for Grade 6, the following mean values and quantitative descriptions were used.

Mean Value **Qualitative Description**

4.20 -5.00	Always Utilized
3.40-4.19	Very Often Utilized
2.60-3.39	Often Utilized
1.80-2.59	Seldom Utilized
1.00-1.79	Never Utilized

To determine the problems met by the teachers in developing Science performance standards for Grade 6, the following mean values and qualitative descriptions were used.

Mean Value **Qualitative Description**

4.40-5.00	Always a problem
3.50-4.39	Oftentimes a problem
3.10-3.49	Sometimes a problem
2.10-3.09	Seldom a problem
1.00-2.09	Never a problem

IV. CONCLUSION

The study revealed that the Grade 6 pupils' performance in Science was generally low, with a mean percentage score of 46%, indicating that the learners were low performing. Several performance standards were found to be inadequately developed, particularly skills related to classifying materials, understanding body systems, identifying vertebrates and invertebrates, caring for animals, and explaining plant reproductive systems.

The results also showed that instructional materials such as learning kits, modular lesson-type materials, and laboratory exercises were seldom utilized, while interactive learning tasks were never utilized. Moreover, major problems affecting Science instruction included the absence or lack of instructional materials and inadequate Science facilities and equipment.

Given these findings, it can be concluded that there is a strong need to develop and implement Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6. Strengthening the use of engaging, activity-based, and resource-supported instructional materials is essential to improve learners' performance and to address the identified gaps in performance standards.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that the Science teacher should properly utilize the Interactive Learning Tasks in Science, and provide pupils with individual copy. Maximum utilization of the Interactive Learning Tasks in Science is vital to serve its purpose.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This journal is an output of the researchers in the degree of Doctor of Education Major in Educational Management and Development at the Cebu Technological University-Main Campus, Cebu City, Philippines, as requirement of our subject in Education Management with Action Research.

The completion of this action research entitled *Interactive Learning Tasks in Science for Grade 6 in Caloy-ahan Elementary School* would not have been possible without the support, guidance, and encouragement of several individuals who generously shared their time, knowledge, and assistance.

First and foremost, heartfelt gratitude is extended to the school head for the approval and encouragement to conduct this study. The guidance and administrative support provided throughout the research process greatly contributed to the successful completion of this work.

Sincere appreciation is also given to the Grade 6 pupils of Caloy-ahan Elementary School, whose participation, cooperation, and enthusiasm made this action research meaningful and relevant. Their willingness to engage in the interactive learning tasks served as the foundation of this study.

Special thanks are extended to fellow teachers and colleagues for their valuable suggestions, insights, and moral support. Their shared experiences and constructive feedback helped refine the development of the modules and strengthened the overall quality of the research.

Gratitude is likewise offered to our family and loved ones for their unwavering encouragement, patience, and understanding during the conduct of this study. Their support provided the motivation needed to accomplish this endeavor.

Above all, the researchers offers deepest thanks to God Almighty for the wisdom, strength, and perseverance granted throughout the entire process.

This work is humbly dedicated to the continuous improvement of Science instruction and to the learners who inspire educators to innovate and strive for excellence.

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